

**An Integrative Approach including Panchakarma and Marma Therapy, administered
in a Spiritual Environment, for the Management of Hemiparesis (Ardhangavata)
Associated with Brain Arteriovenous Malformation (AVM) - A Case Study
(Case Study 12)**

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Abstract

A case report about a female patient has been presented here, who was suffering from various symptoms like left side Hemiparesis (Ardhangavata) and seizures associated with Brain Arteriovenous Malformation (AVM), as well as some other ailments.

Based on the principles of Ayurveda, an integrative approach including Panchakarma and Marma Therapy, was administered to the patient, in a Spiritual Environment, over a period of 11 days (wherein no therapy was administered on the 5th day).

The patient experienced notable relief in various symptoms, wherein, for rigidity present in left hand and left leg there was more than 50% relief; for not able to open left fingers and palm there was ~80% relief; for lower backache there was ~80% relief. Overall, the patient was feeling confident and happy after taking the therapy.

Thus, integrative approach including Panchakarma and Marma Therapy, administered in a Spiritual Environment, showed encouraging results in the management of left side Hemiparesis (Ardhangavata), as well as some other ailments, in a short duration of time.

Keywords: Brain Arteriovenous Malformation, Hemiparesis, Ardhangavata, Seizure, Ayurveda, Panchakarma, Marma Therapy, Herbal Medicine, Spiritual Environment, Gayatri Mantra

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1. Introduction

This case report is about a female patient (age 32 years) who had symptoms associated with Hemiparesis, and some other complaints including:

- Left side Hemiparesis (due to old case of Brain Arteriovenous Malformation (AVM) – right frontal – diagnosed 17 years ago), with seizure (mild, during sleep)
- Weakness
- Hair Fall (severe) with dandruff
- Numbness in extremities (sometimes) (due to exertion and stress)
- Painful menses (duration 3-4 days, cycle 28-30 days)
- Lower backache
- Weight gain (20 kg within 2 years) (height was 157 cm and weight was 75 kg)
- Facial hair growth present
- Disbalanced gait

The patient was taking medication Oxcarbazepine 450mg BD.

Patient's Vitamin D and B12 levels were lower than normal

The patient had no past history of diabetes mellitus, hypertension, asthma, ischemic heart disease (IHD), hypothyroidism

The patient had past history of Cholecystectomy 6 years back

The patient had constipation and gastric upset.

The patient had normal appetite, and normal sleep.

Under Ashtavidha Pariksha of Ayurveda:

Mutra (toilet) was yellowish and holding capacity was low.

Mala (feces) was sometimes hard – due to change of diet.

Jihva (tongue) had pigmentation on both sides.

Shabda was normal.

Sparsha was sometimes warm / sometimes cold (coldness in left half of the body)

Drig – right eye slight squint

Akriti – not normal - left half of the body pulling down

Based on the above mentioned medical history, and further discussion with the doctor, the patient was an old case of Brain Arteriovenous Malformation (AVM) (diagnosed 17 years ago), and the diagnosis for the patient was Left Hemiparesis (Ardhangavata), with seizure, with hair fall.

2. Methodology

Informed consent was obtained from the patient before the start of the therapy.

The prescribed therapeutic interventions were as follows:

2.1 Therapeutic Intervention

As mentioned above, the patient was an old case of Brain Arteriovenous Malformation (AVM) (diagnosed 17 years ago and subsequently treated with surgery and gamma knife embolization), and the diagnosis for the patient was Left Hemiparesis (Ardhangavata), with seizure, with hair fall. Furthermore, the patient had come to the Out

Patient section, and had limited time to take the therapy; hence, the therapeutic intervention was planned accordingly.

Based on Ayurvedic principles, the therapeutic intervention included Panchakarma and Marma Therapy, which was administered to the patient, in a Spiritual Environment, over a period of 11 days (wherein no therapy was administered on the 5th day), as given in Table 1. Details about the method of administration of different therapeutic procedures, given in Table 1, can be found in these references [1-25]. Botanical names of medicinal plants used in the present study can be found in these references [9,11-19].

Some other associated methodologies that were administered, and the advice that was rendered along with the above therapeutic procedure, are as follows.

Dietary restrictions were prescribed. Other behavioral regimen were also prescribed, such as, do not indulge in fear, anxiety, stress, anger, and any other negative thought; do not roam around too much; do not obstruct your natural urges like hunger, thirst, sleep, yawning, tears, etc. Try to keep your mind calm and happy, try to be silent, go early to bed and wake up early in the morning.

The doctor regularly talked to the patient about her condition, and provided both clinical and motivational guidance, i.e. did regular counseling with positive thoughts. Gayatri Mantra was chanted before the start of each therapeutic procedure, as well as played continuously during the therapy. The therapy was administered within the spiritual environment of Dev Sanskriti Vishwavidyalaya, Haridwar.

Table 1: Therapeutic intervention administered to the patient over a period of 11 days (wherein no therapy was administered on the 5th day). The letter 'Y' indicates that the therapeutic procedure mentioned in that row, was administered on that day.

Therapeutic Intervention	Days										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Deepan Pachan (<i>Shankh + Sanjeevani Vati</i>)	Y	Y	Y								
Abhyangam (Sarvanga) (Full Body Massage) with <i>Karpasthyadi Taila + Bala Taila + Mahanarain Taila</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y							
Abhyangam (Ekanga) (Local Massage) of the above oils						Y					
Vashpa Sweda (Sarvanga) (Full Body Steam) of <i>kwath of Dashamoola + Erandamoola</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y							
Nadi Sweda (Local Steam) of <i>kwath of Dashamoola + Erandamoola</i>						Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Koshtha Shuddhi through <i>Virechan Gulika + Avipattikara Churna</i> (at night)				Y							
Basti - Anuvasana with <i>Mahanarain Taila</i>							Y		Y		Y
Basti - Asthapana with <i>Dashamoola + Erandamoola + Nirgundi + Rasna + Nagaramotha + Bala + Giloy + Ashvagandha + Yashtimadhu + Shankhapushpi</i>								Y		Y	
Nasya with <i>Brahmi Ghrith</i> on Days 1,3,4,6,7,8 (numbers represent the number of drops in each nostril)	5	6	7	7		8	8	9			
Nasya with <i>Anu Taila</i> on Day 2											
Kati Basti with <i>Karpasthyadi Taila + Bala Taila + Mahanarain Taila</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y							

Greeva Basti with <i>Karpasthyadi Taila + Bala Taila + Mahanarain Taila</i>						Y	Y	Y			
Kwathdhara with <i>Dashamoola + Brahmi + Jatamansi + Ashvagandha + Yashtimadhu + Shankhapushpi</i>									Y	Y	Y
Dhara Karma with <i>Karpasthyadi Taila + Bala Taila + Mahanarain Taila + Til Taila</i>							Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Lepa (on neck and waist on Days 6,7,8,10,11 and only on neck on Day 9) with paste made from <i>Dashamoola + Erandamoola + Erandabeej (seeds) + Eranda leaves + Dashansh Lepa + Karpasthyadi Taila</i>						Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Kwatha of Dashamoola + Bala + Giloy + Nirgundi + Rasna + Nagaramotha + Ashvagandha + Jatamansi + Brahmi + Shankhapushpi + Yashtimadhu + Amalaki + Daruharidra + Kalamegh</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y		Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Marma Therapy Marma points stimulated - (Upper Extremity – Talahridaya, Kshipra, Manibandha, Koorpara, Indravasti, Ani, Urvi) (Lower Extremity – Talahridaya, Kshipra, Gulpha, Indravasti, Janu, Anu, Urvi) (Back – Ansa) (Head region – Seemant, Adhipati, Apang, Shringatak, Vidhur, Fana)	Y	Y	Y	Y		Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

3. Results

In this case report, the outcomes were assessed in a qualitative (subjective) manner based on the doctor's pre and post examination, and patient's experiential feedback, as given in Table 2.

Table 2: Pre Therapy and Post Therapy Observations

Pre Therapy Observation	Post Therapy Observation
Rigidity present in left hand and left leg	More than 50% improvement
Not able to open left fingers and palm	Almost 80% improvement (can open now)
Lower backache	Almost 80% improvement
Low strength in left half of the body	More than 20% improvement
Constipation present, with gastric upset	Almost 50% relief in constipation; no gastric upset
Disbalanced gait	Slight improvement

Overall, the patient was feeling confident and very happy after the completion of the therapy.

4. Discussion

The present study illustrates the potential of an integrative approach including Panchakarma and Marma Therapy, administered in a Spiritual Environment, for the management left side Hemiparesis (Ardhangavata) associated with Brain Arteriovenous Malformation (AVM), as well as some other ailments.

According to Ayurveda, a healthy human body is supposed to have a relatively stable equilibrium (congenial homeostasis) of Dosha (psycho-biological rhythm - Vata, Pitta, Kapha), Dhatu (body tissues and their nourishing elements) and Mala (excreta) [9,26]; Acharya Sushruta defines health as an equilibrium of Dosha (psycho-biological rhythm), Agni (digestion and metabolism), Dhatu (body tissues), Malakriya (excretory function), as well as the well-being of soul, senses and mind [9,26]. Imbalance in this equilibrium leads to disease, and the aim of the therapy is to restore this balance [9-11]. In view of these Ayurvedic principles, clinical diagnosis of the patient was made, and the integrative approach including Panchakarma and Marma Therapy, was administered to the patient, in a Spiritual Environment.

The results given in Table 2 indicate that the integrative approach including Panchakarma and Marma Therapy, administered in a Spiritual Environment, gives encouraging outcomes, even in short duration. These results may be attributed to the therapeutic action of various Ayurvedic procedures administered to the patient, as well as the effect of Spiritual practices and environment. The mode of action of the Ayurvedic therapeutic procedures have been described in detail in the following references [1-25,27-30].

Each therapy was started with the chanting of Gayatri Mantra, which causes beneficial effects with regards to various physical and mental conditions like attention, concentration, etc. [31-37]. The patient must also have benefited from the spiritually charged environment (which induces constructive inspirations and immense enthusiasm within an individual [38-41]) of Dev Sanskriti Vishwavidyalaya, Haridwar.

Almost daily the doctor talked to the patient about her condition, and provided both

clinical and motivational guidance; the purpose was to instill confidence in the patient that her condition can be improved, and she has to herself take responsibility of bringing about this change by diligently following the prescribed treatment and guidelines.

During Panchakarma therapy, it is advised to avoid '*Ashta-Maha-Doshkar-Bhav*' (eight types of behavioral and dietetic practices that cause obstructions in micro-channels, srotas, leading to aggravation of the diseases) so that better results can be observed. The following of these practices must also have contributed in providing the observed relief.

In place of using a single therapy, a combination of different therapeutic procedures, along with multiple herbs, were used, in order to achieve simultaneous management of the symptoms associated with multiple ailments. Based on Ayurvedic principles, the administered therapeutic procedures and medicinal herbs also had tissue nourishing (*vrinhan*), strengthening (*balya*), and rejuvenating (*rasayan*) effects [2-9,11-15], which must have caused the amount of relief experienced by the patient in such a short duration of therapy.

Although the results are qualitative in nature, yet the degree of benefit attained in addressing the chronic ailments is noteworthy, especially considering the fact that the patient was an Outdoor Patient, had genuine limitations in following the dietary restrictions, and the therapy was administered for quite short duration.

Further in-depth quantitative study would definitely be worthwhile to establish the mode of operation of the administered therapeutic procedure in the light of modern scientific understanding.

5. Conclusions

In the present study, an integrative approach including Panchakarma and Marma Therapy, was administered in a Spiritual Environment, for the management of left side Hemiparesis (Ardhangavata) associated with Brain Arteriovenous Malformation (AVM), as well as some other ailments. A single case study involving female patient was presented. Various therapeutic procedures were administered to the Out Patient section patient over a period of 11 days (wherein no therapy was administered on the 5th day). Qualitative analysis showed encouraging results, with the patient experiencing notable relief in various symptoms associated with chronic complaints, in a short duration of time.

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Compliance with ethical standards

Informed consent was obtained from the patient before the start of the therapy.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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